

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15311416

Predictive Influence of Creative Cognition and Personality Traits on Entrepreneurial Skills Development among Final Year Undergraduate Students in the University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria

Amaechi-Udogu, Vivian Chukwunonyenim (Ph.D)^{1*} & Elusie, Tochukwu Emmanuel²

^{1,2}Department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling,
Faculty of Education,
University of Port Harcourt, Port Harcourt, Nigeria
Email: vivian.amaechi-udogu@uniport.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the predictive influence of creative cognition and personality traits on entrepreneurial skills among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt. Four research questions and four null hypotheses guided the study. A correlational research design was employed, with a population of 5,478 final-year undergraduates. A sample of 550 students was selected using stratified random sampling. Three instruments were used for data collection: the Creative Thinking Questionnaire (CTQ), Personality Traits Questionnaire (PTQ), and Entrepreneurial Skills Development Questionnaire (ESDQ). Reliability coefficients of 0.73, 0.71, and 0.80 were obtained for the CTQ, PTQ, and ESDQ, respectively, using Cronbach's Alpha. Simple and Multiple Regression analyses were employed to answer the research questions, while t-tests and ANOVA were used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. Results indicated that both creative thinking and personality traits significantly predicted entrepreneurial skills among final-year students at the University of Port Harcourt. Based on these findings, it was recommended that the Counselling Unit of the university integrate creative thinking modules into the curriculum to enhance innovation and problem-solving abilities among final-year students.

Keywords: entrepreneurship, creative cognition, personality traits, entrepreneurial skills, Undergraduate students.

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship is increasingly recognized as a critical driver of economic growth and societal development, particularly in emerging economies such as Nigeria. According to the National Bureau of Statistics [NBS], (2023), the country faces an alarming youth unemployment rate of approximately 53% with 33% of them under 30 years old, underscoring the urgent need for entrepreneurship education and the cultivation of entrepreneurial skills (Adeniji, 2024). Entrepreneurship contributes not only to job creation but also to innovation, wealth generation, and economic empowerment, particularly in developing nations like Nigeria (Chukwudi & Nwosu, 2018; Tantawy et al., 2021). This makes the cultivation of entrepreneurship skills a priority for national development and economic sustainability.

Every year, Nigerian universities produce hundreds of thousands of graduates who face an uncertain future in a highly competitive job market. Due to the lack of diversified industries, heavy dependence on oil exports, and insufficient manufacturing sectors, many graduates are left unemployed or underemployed, resulting in heightened frustration, anxiety, and, in extreme cases, depression and even suicide. This situation has also led to an increase in criminal activities, such as internet fraud, ritual killings, kidnapping, and prostitution, as individuals struggle to survive. The need for entrepreneurial skills is more pressing than ever, as these skills not only provide an alternative avenue for self-employment but also play a significant role in mitigating the social unrest caused by unemployment.

In response to these economic realities and the rising graduate unemployment rate, Nigerian universities have integrated entrepreneurship education into their curricula to foster job creation and national development (Oyinlola et al., 2024; Ofor Douglas, 2024; Chukwudi & Nwosu, 2018). However, many graduates still face significant challenges in translating classroom knowledge into real-world entrepreneurial ventures. They often lack the creativity, resilience, and cognitive flexibility necessary for innovation and entrepreneurial success (Ofor Douglas, 2024; Chukwudi & Nwosu, 2018; Yu, et al, 2023; Wu, et al. 2023; Mensah et al., 2021; Hood & Young, 1993; Oyinlola et al., 2024). This highlights the importance of internal psychological constructs such as resilience, self-efficacy, creative cognition, and personality traits in driving entrepreneurial behaviour. While national policies, including the National Policy on Education (2013) and the National Youth Policy (2019), recognize the importance of youth entrepreneurship, they often prioritize technical and managerial skills over cognitive and personality factors that are equally critical for sustained entrepreneurial success.

Entrepreneurial skill development is essential for Nigeria's long-term economic sustainability. Entrepreneurial skills encompass a wide range of abilities such as opportunity recognition, innovation, risk management, financial literacy, leadership, and resilience (OECD, 2019). Entrepreneurial skills development refers to the process through which individuals acquire the knowledge, abilities, and attributes needed to identify opportunities, take initiatives, and manage ventures effectively. However, despite the integration of entrepreneurship education into university curricula, studies have pointed out significant gaps, particularly regarding the cultivation of creative thinking, resilience, and entrepreneurial mindsets among students (Adebayo & Kolawole, 2013; Okoli et al., 2021; Mbon et al, 2023). A considerable number of Nigerian graduates still lack the psychological readiness to translate their entrepreneurial knowledge into action, limiting their ability to launch and sustain successful ventures.

The University of Port Harcourt stands as a leader in the promotion of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria, implementing various innovative initiatives to foster skill acquisition and competency development among its students. Through strategic efforts such as the establishment of the Centre for Entrepreneurial Studies, the university has invested significantly in integrating entrepreneurship into its academic culture. These initiatives are intended to cultivate an entrepreneurial mindset and prepare students for self-employment and leadership roles in an increasingly competitive global economy. However, despite these efforts, observations from the researchers suggest a troubling trend: many students continue to approach entrepreneurship courses with minimal enthusiasm, viewing them primarily as compulsory academic requirements rather than opportunities for self-actualization and career advancement. This attitude raises concerns about the internalization of entrepreneurial values and the ability to translate formal education into practical entrepreneurial outcomes.

This brings into question whether students at the University of Port Harcourt are being sufficiently equipped with the necessary cognitive and personality traits that support entrepreneurial success. Specifically, it calls into focus whether students possess the creative cognitive abilities essential for recognizing opportunities, solving problems, and innovating. Furthermore, do students have the required personality traits, such as resilience, initiative, and adaptability, which are critical for navigating the complexities of the entrepreneurial landscape? These questions are central to understanding the development of entrepreneurship skills among students and their ability to translate academic knowledge into tangible entrepreneurial ventures. The development of entrepreneurial skills, as the dependent

variable in this study, hinges on the interplay of cognitive factors like creativity and personality traits that influence students' entrepreneurial skills. Therefore, it is essential to explore how these factors contribute to the development of entrepreneurial skills and whether they are being adequately addressed in the university's programs.

Creativity is broadly defined as the ability of an individual to produce ideas, solutions, or products that are both novel and valuable (Runco, 2023). This process involves two key cognitive processes: divergent thinking and convergent thinking. Divergent thinking is responsible for generating a wide range of potential ideas, while convergent thinking focuses on evaluating and selecting the most suitable or appropriate idea from the pool of possibilities. These two cognitive functions are essential for the creative process, allowing individuals to move from broad exploration to focused innovation. Creative cognition, on the other hand, refers to the mental processes that underpin the generation of novel and useful ideas (Lebuda & Benedek, 2023). These cognitive processes go beyond mere idea generation, incorporating aspects such as metacognitive regulation, where individuals monitor and refine their creative efforts. In this sense, creative cognition involves a more complex interplay between ideation, evaluation, and adaptation, ensuring that ideas not only emerge but are also effectively honed to meet specific goals or standards of value. This dynamic cognitive process highlights the intricate mechanisms that support creativity, making it essential for innovation and problem-solving across various domains.

Similarly, Ward et al, 1999) sees creative cognition as the mental processes that enable individuals to generate, evaluate, and implement novel and useful ideas. It encompasses various cognitive functions such as divergent thinking, problem-solving, and idea generation, all of which contribute to an individual's ability to develop unique solutions. Furthermore, creative cognition plays a critical role in entrepreneurial success, as it allows entrepreneurs to identify unmet needs, devise innovative strategies, and adapt to changing market conditions. To Runco and Acar (2012), creative cognition is foundational to entrepreneurial activity because it fosters innovation, flexibility, and originality which are two crucial qualities essential for entrepreneurs who seek to differentiate themselves in competitive markets. Moreover, entrepreneurs who excel in creative cognition often thrive in sectors that require novel solutions and innovative approaches. These sectors typically demand out-of-the-box thinking to navigate complex challenges. In the context of Nigeria's entrepreneurial landscape, which is often shaped by non-traditional sectors, creative thinking becomes even more indispensable. Nigeria, grappling with challenges such as high unemployment rates, limited access to quality education, and infrastructural deficits, calls for entrepreneurs who can develop innovative solutions to these pressing issues.

In addition, studies have shown that embedding creativity within educational systems significantly enhances students' abilities to generate business ideas, solve problems, and recognize opportunities (Alhadihaq et al., 2024; Hamidi et al., 2008). This underscores the importance of integrating creative cognition into curricula, particularly in entrepreneurship education, to better equip students with the cognitive tools necessary to navigate the business world successfully. Similarly, fostering creative thinking in educational settings provides students with the mental framework to approach challenges with innovation and originality. By encouraging divergent thinking and problem-solving skills, educational institutions play a pivotal role in preparing students to become effective entrepreneurs who can bring creative and sustainable solutions to Nigeria's socio-economic challenges. Similarly, Mumford et al. (2020) argue that creativity is vital not only for generating ideas but also for problem-solving in unpredictable, high-stakes situations. The ability to think innovatively and navigate volatile environments is critical in emerging economies like Nigeria, where entrepreneurs contend with resource scarcity and regulatory instability. Thus, creative cognition fosters the resilience and adaptability indispensable for entrepreneurial success (Usoro & Brown, 2024).

Several studies corroborate this assertion, Zampetakis and Moustakis (2006) found that students with higher creative cognition scores were more likely to demonstrate entrepreneurial intentions. Adenuga and Ayodele (2013) reported that students with higher creative potential were more likely to develop business plans and initiate ventures. Similarly, Obialo (2020) concluded that fostering creative cognition among

Nigerian students significantly enhances entrepreneurial outcomes, contributing to job creation and economic development. Liu et al. (2022) emphasized that creative cognition is crucial for venture ideation and resilience during uncertainty, reinforcing the notion that creative thinking is essential and not merely beneficial for entrepreneurship. Moreover, several studies, confirm that creative cognition is central to entrepreneurial innovation and opportunity recognition (Alhadihaq et al., 2024; Runco & Acar, 2012). Uzonwanne-Obianefo et al. (2021) also, found out in their study, that Nigerian students with higher levels of creative cognition were more likely to engage in entrepreneurial activities post-graduation, demonstrating greater problem-solving skills and stronger innovative capacities which are both essential in Nigeria's challenging economic

In addition to creative cognition, personality traits may also play a significant role in influencing entrepreneurial behaviour. These traits, which form the foundation of an individual's behavioural patterns, are essential for understanding how individuals approach entrepreneurial challenges and opportunities. Amaechi-Udogu (2020) conceptualize personality traits as enduring patterns of thought, behaviour, and emotion that define an individual uniquely. These traits are shaped by biological predispositions, psychosocial development, and life experiences, and they influence key entrepreneurial behaviours. Personality traits play a pivotal role in shaping entrepreneurial outcomes, influencing critical aspects such as opportunity recognition, risk-taking, resilience, and innovation (Rauch & Frese, 2007; Zhao & Seibert, 2006; Chen, 2024, Kollmann, et al, 2021; Cao, et al, 2022). Entrepreneurs with distinct personality characteristics tend to approach the uncertainties and challenges of business with varying levels of creativity, persistence, and proactivity.

The Big Five Personality Traits model developed by Paul Costa and Robert McCrae is a psychological framework that identifies five broad dimensions of human personality, which includes Openness to Experience, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Neuroticism (Costa & McCrae, 1992, 1996). Each of these traits influences entrepreneurial behaviours in distinct ways, providing valuable insights into how different individuals approach entrepreneurship. Openness to Experience, for instance, is characterized by a high degree of creativity, curiosity, and a willingness to embrace novelty. Individuals with high Openness are more likely to engage in innovative entrepreneurial activities and adapt to change. Research by Leutner et al. (2014) and Zhao & Seibert (2006) has demonstrated that high Openness is positively correlated with entrepreneurship, as individuals with this trait are better able to recognize and seize opportunities in uncertain environments. Uche and Adegboyega (2022) found that students with high Openness exhibited stronger entrepreneurial intentions, engaging in business activities during their studies and showcasing greater adaptability to the business environment.

Conscientiousness, on the other hand, is marked by goal-setting, persistence, and a strong sense of responsibility. Entrepreneurs with high Conscientiousness are organized, disciplined, and tend to persist in the face of setbacks. This trait is crucial for strategic planning and the successful execution of long-term business goals. Khalaf, (2024) highlight that Conscientiousness is associated with greater perseverance and the ability to overcome challenges. In a similar vein, Uche & Adegboyega (2022) reported that Nigerian students who scored high in Conscientiousness were more likely to engage in entrepreneurial ventures, demonstrating a focus on long-term goals and a high level of discipline in their business pursuits. The trait fosters an entrepreneurial mindset that is both goal-oriented and resilient, characteristics that are essential for building sustainable businesses.

Extraversion is another personality trait that significantly impacts entrepreneurship. Extraverted individuals are sociable, assertive, and energetic, which are qualities that facilitate networking, leadership, and the ability to influence others. These traits are particularly beneficial for entrepreneurs who must engage with customers, investors, and partners. Zhao & Seibert (2006) argue that Extraversion enhances entrepreneurial outcomes by improving one's ability to network and establish connections that are vital for business growth. Research by Obschonka & Stuetzer (2017) further supports this by demonstrating that Extraversion is positively correlated with entrepreneurial behaviour, as these individuals are more likely to take the initiative, engage with others, and establish relationships that can foster business

success. Uche & Adegboyega (2022) found that students with high Extraversion scores were more inclined to pursue entrepreneurial ventures, leveraging their social skills to build networks and collaborate effectively with others.

While Extraversion promotes collaboration and leadership, Agreeableness, which is characterized by traits such as empathy, cooperation, and the ability to maintain harmonious relationships, can also influence entrepreneurship. However, excessive Agreeableness may hinder entrepreneurial success. Entrepreneurs who are overly agreeable may struggle with negotiation, assertive decision-making, and taking a firm stand when necessary. Zhao & Seibert (2006) note that while Agreeableness can foster teamwork and trust, it may also prevent entrepreneurs from making tough decisions that are essential for the growth of their businesses. Leutner et al. (2014) emphasize the need for a balance between Agreeableness and assertiveness, as excessive Agreeableness may hinder an entrepreneur's ability to navigate competitive environments effectively. Uche & Adegboyega (2022) found that students with moderate Agreeableness were more likely to work well in teams, but those who scored too highly on this trait found it difficult to assert themselves in business negotiations, which can impede entrepreneurial progress.

Finally, Neuroticism, which is marked by emotional instability, anxiety, and a tendency to experience negative emotions, poses significant challenges for entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurs with high levels of Neuroticism are likely to struggle with stress management, decision-making, and risk-taking, all of which are critical in business. Zhao & Seibert (2006) and Rauch & Frese (2007) emphasize that high Neuroticism negatively impacts entrepreneurial success by hindering an individual's ability to manage the inevitable stress and uncertainty of entrepreneurship. Uche & Adegboyega (2022) found that students with high Neuroticism exhibited lower entrepreneurial intentions, as their emotional instability made them less likely to take entrepreneurial risks or persist in the face of challenges. This aligns with existing literature that links emotional instability to poor entrepreneurial outcomes, as it inhibits proactive decision-making and the ability to cope with the demands of entrepreneurship.

Recent studies have begun to explore the interaction between creative cognition and personality traits in influencing entrepreneurial outcomes. Li, et al, (2022) reported that the relationship between personality traits and entrepreneurship is mediated by creative cognition. Individuals who are high in Openness and Conscientiousness, combined with strong creative cognition, are more likely to generate innovative business ideas and pursue them with persistence and dedication. Similarly, Sun et al. (2022) found that students with high levels of Openness and creative cognition exhibited enhanced resilience and adaptability in entrepreneurial contexts. These individuals were more equipped to handle the uncertainty and risks involved in launching and sustaining businesses. Additionally, Liu et al. (2022) also found that the combination of creative cognition and personality traits such as Conscientiousness contributed to higher entrepreneurial success. This highlights the importance of integrating creative thinking and personality development in entrepreneurship education, as these psychological factors collectively enhance entrepreneurial capabilities.

It is the researchers' opinion that in the Nigerian educational setting, integrating creative cognition and personality development into entrepreneurship education is essential. While many Nigerian universities emphasize technical skills, they often neglect the psychological attributes critical for entrepreneurial success. The ability to innovate, take risks, and persevere despite challenges requires a combination of cognitive abilities and personality traits that traditional curricula do not sufficiently nurture. Against this backdrop, the researchers investigated the predictive influence of creative cognition and personality traits on entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria. Although entrepreneurship education has gained significant traction across Nigerian universities, existing empirical evidence suggests that exposure to entrepreneurship courses alone is insufficient to cultivate entrepreneurial skills (Mensah et al., 2021; Oyinlola et al., 2024; Okoli et al., 2021). Psychological readiness, creativity, and personality-driven motivation are key factors that determine whether students develop the entrepreneurial skills necessary for successful business

creation and management. By focusing on final-year students, who are at a critical stage of transition into the professional world, this study captures a crucial phase where entrepreneurial skills are expected to mature and be applied practically. Understanding the influence of creative cognition and personality traits on entrepreneurial skills development among this group will provide valuable insights for curriculum designers, educators, policymakers, and career counsellors. Fostering entrepreneurial skills through the deliberate cultivation of creative cognitive abilities and essential personality traits offers a transformative approach to addressing Nigeria's youth unemployment crisis, promoting self-reliance, and stimulating sustainable economic growth.

Statement of the Problem

Youth unemployment persists as one of the most pressing socio-economic challenges in Nigeria. Annually, Nigerian universities graduate hundreds of thousands of students who must navigate an increasingly saturated and competitive Labor market. The nation's limited industry diversification, over-reliance on oil exports, and underdeveloped manufacturing sector have contributed significantly to the growing rates of graduate unemployment and underemployment. Consequently, many young Nigerians experience profound economic and emotional distress, often manifesting as anxiety, frustration, and depression. In more severe cases, these conditions have fuelled a rise in social vices, including internet fraud, ritual killings, kidnapping, and prostitution, as many individuals resort to desperate means for survival. In response to this escalating crisis, entrepreneurship has been widely promoted as a viable strategy for fostering job creation, economic empowerment, and innovation. While entrepreneurship education has been increasingly incorporated into academic curricula, there remains a limited understanding of the psychological factors that underpin entrepreneurial success, particularly among Nigerian university students. Much of the existing discourse has emphasized the acquisition of technical knowledge and business skills, often neglecting the critical role of psychological attributes such as creativity and personality traits in cultivating entrepreneurial competencies. Creative cognition the mental process involved in producing novel and useful ideas and personality characteristics are recognized as essential drivers of entrepreneurial behaviour and success. Nevertheless, empirical research exploring the specific contribution of these psychological factors to entrepreneurial skill development within the Nigerian university context remains scarce. This knowledge gap is concerning, as it impedes the ability of educational institutions to design interventions that holistically prepare students for entrepreneurial endeavours.

It is against this backdrop, that the present study examined the predictive influence of creative cognition and personality traits on entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt. By investigating how these psychological factors shape entrepreneurial competencies, the study aimed to provide evidence-based insights that can guide educational reforms and policies geared towards enhancing students' readiness for an increasingly entrepreneurship-driven economy.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate the predictive influence of creative cognition and personality traits on entrepreneurial skills among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt. The specific objectives of this study were to:

1. Ascertain the extent to which creative cognition predicts entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt.
2. Investigate the joint prediction of personality traits on entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt.
3. Examine the independent prediction of personality traits on entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt.
4. Assess the joint prediction of creative cognition and personality traits on entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. To what extent does creative cognition predict entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt?
2. To what extent do personality traits jointly predict entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt?
3. To what extent do personality traits independently predict entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt?
4. To what extent do creative cognition and personality traits jointly predict entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested for significance at a level of 0.05:

1. Creative cognition does not significantly predict entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt.
2. Personality traits do not significantly and jointly predict entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt.
3. Personality traits do not significantly and independently predict entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt.
4. Creative cognition and personality traits do not significantly and jointly predict entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a correlational research design in investigating the predictive influence of creative cognition and personality traits on predict entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt. The target population comprises of 5,478 final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt. A sample of 550 students was selected using stratified random sampling. Data were collected using three standardized questionnaires: Creative Cognition Inventory (Guilford, 1967). Big Five Personality Traits Inventory (Costa & McCrae, 1992) and Entrepreneurial Skill Scale (Manimala, 2005). The instruments used a four-point Likert scale: Very High Extent (VHE) = 4, High Extent (HE) = 3, Low Extent (LE) = 2, and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1. The Creative Cognitive Questionnaire contained 20 items, the Personality Traits Questionnaire had 40 items, and the Entrepreneurial Skills Questionnaire included 25 items. The validity of the instruments was ensured experts' psychometricians judgement and factor analysis. To test reliability, the researcher used the Cronbach Alpha method, administering the instruments to 20 respondents not involved in the main study. The resulting Cronbach Alpha values were 0.73 for the Creative Cognitive Questionnaire, 0.71 for the Personality Traits Questionnaire, and 0.80 for the Entrepreneurial Skills Questionnaire, indicating good reliability. The data collection process involved administering 550 copies of the questionnaires. Prior to distribution, the researcher explained the purpose of the study and assured respondents of the confidentiality of their responses. The questionnaires were distributed and collected on the spot, with the assistance of five trained research assistants. Data analysis was analysed using Simple and Multiple Regression analysis to answer the research questions while t-test and Anova associated with regression were used to test the hypotheses at a 0,05 level of significance level. This method was chosen to evaluate the predictive power of creative cognition and personality traits on entrepreneurial skills development.

RESULTS

Research Questions One: *To what extent does creative cognition predict entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt?*

To answer this research question, a simple linear regression analysis was performed to examine the predictive influence of creative cognition on entrepreneurial skills development. The result of the analysis is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Regression Model summary of the extent creative cognition predicts entrepreneurial skills development among final year undergraduate students in University of Port Harcourt

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.741	.520	.501	.58568

a. Predictors: (Constant), Creative cognition

As shown in Table 1, the regression analysis yielded an R value of 0.741, indicating a strong positive relationship between creative cognition and entrepreneurial skills development. The R Square value of 0.520 suggests that creative cognition accounts for approximately 52% of the variance observed in entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students. Furthermore, the adjusted R Square value of 0.501 indicates that, after adjusting for the number of predictors, creative cognition still explains about 50.1% of the variability in entrepreneurial skills development. The standard error of the estimate was 0.58568, suggests an acceptable level of predictive accuracy. Overall, the result demonstrates that creative cognition positively predicts entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt.

Ho₁: Creative cognition does not significantly predict entrepreneurial skills development among final year undergraduate students in University of Port Harcourt.

In order to test this hypothesis, a simple linear regression analysis was conducted, and the t-test associated with the regression model is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: t-test associated with simple regression on the extent creative cognition predicts entrepreneurial skills development among final year undergraduate students in University of Port Harcourt

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	23.417	.195		12.385	.000
	Creative Cognition	.741	.61	.746	3.649	.000

The result in Table 2 shows that creative cognition significantly predicts entrepreneurial skills development ($\beta = 0.746$, $t = 3.649$, $p < 0.05$). Since the p-value (.000) is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis (Ho₁) is rejected. This indicates that creative cognition has a significant positive influence on entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt. Thus, the finding implies that students who demonstrate higher levels of creative cognition are more likely to develop stronger entrepreneurial skills.

Research Questions Two: *To what extent does personality traits joint predict entrepreneurial skills development among final year undergraduate students in University of Port Harcourt?*

To determine the extent to which personality traits jointly predict entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt, a multiple regression analysis was conducted. The model summary of the analysis is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Model summary of the extent personality traits joint predicts entrepreneurial skills development among final year undergraduate students in University of Port Harcourt

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.556 ^a	.309	.295	.50585

As shown in Table 3, the model produced an R-value of 0.556, indicating a moderate positive relationship between personality traits and entrepreneurial skills development. The R Square value of 0.309 suggests that approximately 30.9% of the variance in entrepreneurial skills development among the students can be explained by their personality traits. The adjusted R Square value of 0.295 further confirms the model's moderate predictive power after accounting for the number of predictors. This results implies that personality traits jointly contribute meaningfully to the development of entrepreneurial skills among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt.

Ho₂: Personality traits do not significantly predict entrepreneurial skills jointly among final year undergraduate students in University of Port Harcourt.

To test this hypothesis, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) associated with the multiple regression analysis was conducted. The result is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Analysis of variance of regression of the extent personality traits joint predicts entrepreneurial skills development among final year undergraduate students in University of Port Harcourt

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	27.965	5	5.593	21.858	.000 ^b
	Residual	62.435	544	.256		
	Total	90.400	549			

The result in Table 4 shows that the F-value of 21.858 is statistically significant at $p < .05$ (Sig. = .000). This indicates that personality traits jointly have a significant predictive influence on entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt. Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho₂) which stated that personality traits do not significantly predict entrepreneurial skills development jointly is rejected. This finding implies that personality traits are important psychological factors that contribute significantly to the development of entrepreneurial skills among university students.

Research Questions Three: *To what does personality traits independently predicts entrepreneurial skills development among final year undergraduate students in University of Port Harcourt?*

Ho₃: Personality traits do not significantly and independently predict entrepreneurial

To test this hypothesis, a multiple regression analysis was performed to determine the extent to which each personality trait independently contributed to entrepreneurial skills development.

Table 5: t-test associated with multiple regression showing the extent personality traits independently predicts entrepreneurial skills among final year undergraduate students in University of Port Harcourt

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	1.799	.251		7.180	.000
	Neuroticism	.046	.045	.065	1.042	.298
	Extraversion	.383	.062	.410	6.224	.000
	Open to experience	.186	.064	.197	2.916	.004
	Conscientiousness	.177	.087	.148	2.045	.042
	Agreeableness	.061	.050	.074	1.210	.228

The results presented in Table 5 show the t-test associated with multiple regression analysis, revealing the extent to which each personality trait independently predicts entrepreneurial skills development. The constant (intercept) is 1.799, which is significant with a p-value of 0.000. Neuroticism has an unstandardized coefficient of 0.046 with a standardized beta of 0.065. The t-value of 1.042 and p-value of

0.298 indicate that neuroticism does not significantly predict entrepreneurial skills development, so the null hypothesis is accepted. Extraversion has an unstandardized coefficient of 0.383 with a standardized beta of 0.410. The t-value of 6.224 and p-value of 0.000 show that extraversion significantly predicts entrepreneurial skills development, so the null hypothesis is rejected. Openness to experience has an unstandardized coefficient of 0.186 with a standardized beta of 0.197. The t-value of 2.916 and p-value of 0.004 indicate that openness to experience significantly predicts entrepreneurial skills development, so the null hypothesis is rejected. Conscientiousness has an unstandardized coefficient of 0.177 with a standardized beta of 0.148. The t-value of 2.045 and p-value of 0.042 indicate that conscientiousness significantly predicts entrepreneurial skills development, so the null hypothesis is rejected. Agreeableness has an unstandardized coefficient of 0.061 with a standardized beta of 0.074. The t-value of 1.210 and p-value of 0.228 indicate that agreeableness does not significantly predict entrepreneurial skills development, so the null hypothesis is accepted. The null hypothesis (Ho₃) that personality traits do not significantly and independently predict entrepreneurial skills development is rejected, as extraversion, openness to experience, and conscientiousness significantly predict entrepreneurial skills development, while neuroticism and agreeableness do not. This suggests that traits such as extraversion and openness to experience are more influential in fostering entrepreneurial skills.

Research Questions Four: *To what extent do creative cognition and personality traits joint prediction entrepreneurial skills development among final year undergraduate students in University of Port Harcourt?*

Table 6: Model summary of the extent creative cognition and personality traits joint prediction entrepreneurial skills development among final year undergraduate students in University of Port Harcourt

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.771 ^a	.537	.530	.55953

The results presented in Table 6 showed that the model yielded an R value of .771, indicating a strong positive relationship between the combined predictors (creative cognition and personality traits) and entrepreneurial skills development. The R Square value of .537 revealed that approximately 53.7% of the variance in entrepreneurial skills development among the students could be jointly explained by creative cognition and personality traits. The Adjusted R Square value of .530 further confirmed the robustness of the model, accounting for slight adjustments due to sample size. The standard error of the estimate (.55953) indicated a reasonable level of accuracy in the predictions. These findings demonstrate that the combined effect of creative cognition and personality traits provides a substantial and meaningful contribution to the development of entrepreneurial skills among final-year students.

Ho₄: Creative cognition and personality traits jointly do not significantly predict entrepreneurial skills development among final year undergraduate students in University of Port Harcourt.

To test this hypothesis, an analysis of variance (ANOVA) associated with the multiple regression model was conducted.

Table 7: Analysis of variance of regression of the extent creative cognitive and personality traits joint prediction entrepreneurial skills development among final year undergraduate students in University of Port Harcourt

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	12.307	2	6.154	19.655	.000 ^b
	Residual	77.329	547	.139		
	Total	89.636	549			

As shown in Table 7, the regression model produced an F-value of 19.655, which was found to be statistically significant at the .000 level. This result indicates that the joint contribution of creative cognition and personality traits to entrepreneurial skills development is significant. Consequently, the null

hypothesis was rejected. This implies that creative cognition and personality traits together significantly predict entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students in the University of Port Harcourt.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study investigated the predictive influence of creative cognition and personality traits on entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt. The results provide significant insights into how both cognitive and personality factors contribute to the enhancement of entrepreneurial capabilities, reaffirming the critical role they play in shaping entrepreneurial outcomes. Creative cognition emerged as a strong predictor of entrepreneurial skills development, underscoring the importance of cognitive processes in entrepreneurial success. Creative cognition, defined as the ability to generate novel and valuable ideas, is integral to opportunity identification and effective problem-solving (Lebuda & Benedek, 2023). The findings align with previous research indicating that higher levels of creative cognition are associated with increased entrepreneurial intentions and behaviours. Zampetakis and Moustakis (2006) reported that students with greater creative cognitive abilities were more likely to initiate entrepreneurial ventures and engage in innovative behaviours. Similarly, Obialo (2020) highlighted that fostering creative cognition among Nigerian students significantly enhances their entrepreneurial outcomes.

In this study, students with higher creative cognition scores demonstrated superior abilities to generate business ideas, recognize market gaps, and solve complex entrepreneurial challenges. This finding resonates with the work of Liu et al. (2022) and Uzonwanne et al. (2022), who emphasized the critical role of creative cognition in venture ideation and resilience during uncertain market conditions. Creative cognition, through its combination of divergent and convergent thinking, empowers students to identify novel solutions to business problems, thereby reinforcing the argument that creativity is a cornerstone of entrepreneurial success.

Additionally, creative cognition facilitates adaptive problem-solving and innovation, which are particularly vital within Nigeria's dynamic and often unpredictable entrepreneurial landscape (Runco & Acar, 2012). Students possessing strong creative cognition skills are better equipped to navigate the challenges imposed by Nigeria's infrastructural limitations and socio-economic constraints (Alhadihaq et al., 2024). Thus, creative cognition transcends being merely an academic trait and becomes a practical skill essential for driving real-world entrepreneurial success, particularly in resource-constrained settings.

The findings of the present study also revealed significant contributions of personality traits specifically Openness to Experience, Conscientiousness, and Extraversion, in predicting entrepreneurial skills development. These results are consistent with the Big Five Personality Traits model, which has been widely applied to understand entrepreneurial behaviours. Openness to Experience, characterized by curiosity, creativity, and adaptability, was found to be positively associated with entrepreneurial intentions. This corroborates previous findings by Leutner et al. (2014) and Zhao and Seibert (2006), who reported that individuals high in Openness are more inclined toward entrepreneurial activities due to their cognitive flexibility in recognizing and exploiting opportunities.

Similarly, Conscientiousness emerged as a strong predictor of entrepreneurial skills. Conscientious individuals, known for goal-setting, persistence, and responsibility, tend to exhibit higher levels of perseverance and strategic planning, essential traits for long-term entrepreneurial success (Khalaf, 2024). This finding supports the work of Uche and Adegboyega (2022), who observed that students with high Conscientiousness scores demonstrated stronger entrepreneurial orientation and engagement in sustainable business practices. By promoting discipline and a structured approach to goal attainment, Conscientiousness enables students to translate entrepreneurial knowledge into effective action.

Furthermore, Extraversion significantly and positively influenced entrepreneurial skills development. Extraverted individuals are sociable, assertive, and proactive—traits particularly beneficial in entrepreneurship, where building relationships with customers, investors, and partners is critical (Zhao &

Seibert, 2006). This finding aligns with the work of Obschonka and Stuetzer (2017), who found that extraverted individuals are more likely to initiate and sustain entrepreneurial ventures due to their enhanced social and leadership capabilities. Among the University of Port Harcourt students, those who scored high on Extraversion exhibited stronger leadership skills and greater social engagement, which contributed meaningfully to their entrepreneurial development.

Conversely, Agreeableness and Neuroticism exhibited mixed effects on entrepreneurial skills. While moderate levels of Agreeableness, characterized by cooperation and teamwork, were found beneficial, excessive Agreeableness could potentially hinder entrepreneurial outcomes by compromising assertiveness during negotiations and decision-making processes (Leutner et al., 2014; Zhao & Seibert, 2006). Students who exhibited moderate Agreeableness achieved better entrepreneurial outcomes by balancing collaboration with assertiveness, a crucial trait for navigating competitive business environments.

Regarding Neuroticism, the findings revealed a negative impact on entrepreneurial skills development. Students with high Neuroticism levels, characterized by emotional instability and susceptibility to stress, were less likely to engage in risk-taking and to persist through entrepreneurial challenges (Zhao & Seibert, 2006). This result corroborates Uche and Adegboyega (2022), who similarly found that emotional instability impedes entrepreneurial intentions and success.

The interaction between creative cognition and personality traits further illuminates the complexity of entrepreneurial skills development. The synergy observed in this study reflects the assertion by Li et al. (2022) that the relationship between personality traits and entrepreneurship is often mediated by creative cognition. Students who combined high levels of Openness, Conscientiousness, and Extraversion with strong creative thinking abilities were more likely to generate innovative business ideas, demonstrate resilience, and sustain entrepreneurial pursuits.

Similarly, the findings align with those of Sun et al. (2022) and Liu et al. (2022), who reported that integrating creative cognition with key personality traits enhances entrepreneurial resilience and success. This suggests that entrepreneurship education should not only emphasize cognitive skills like creative thinking but also foster personality traits such as Openness, Conscientiousness, and Extraversion to prepare students for the multifaceted challenges of entrepreneurial endeavours. Ultimately, this study affirms that entrepreneurial success is not solely a function of cognitive ability or personality traits in isolation, but rather the dynamic interplay between the two. This is consistent with the proposition by Runco and Acar (2012), who argued that creativity amplifies the expression of personality traits within entrepreneurial contexts, facilitating innovative idea generation and the capacity to overcome obstacles.

These findings collectively highlight that fostering both creativity and positive personality dispositions can significantly enhance entrepreneurial capacity among university students. They also suggest that interventions aimed at nurturing creative thinking and developing entrepreneurial personality traits could play a pivotal role in preparing students for successful entrepreneurial careers, particularly within the Nigerian educational and socio-economic context.

Implications and Recommendations

1. Nigerian universities should revise entrepreneurship education curricula to integrate modules that explicitly teach creative problem-solving, innovation management, design thinking, and critical reasoning. Emphasis should be placed on experiential learning methods, including simulations, real-life projects, and business incubation activities that stimulate entrepreneurial competencies.
2. Universities should establish structured training programs aimed at nurturing key personality traits such as openness, conscientiousness, and emotional resilience, linked to entrepreneurial success. These programs should incorporate emotional intelligence, leadership, communication, and adaptability skills to holistically prepare students for entrepreneurial challenges.
3. Institutions should invest in setting up interdisciplinary innovation hubs that foster collaboration among students from diverse academic backgrounds. These hubs should serve as centers for

creativity, business idea development, mentorship by successful entrepreneurs, and practical entrepreneurship exposure.

4. University counselling units should embed entrepreneurial guidance services within their frameworks, offering individualized personality assessments, entrepreneurial aptitude profiling, and tailored counselling interventions to support students' entrepreneurial aspirations and psychological readiness.
5. Higher education policymakers and university management should formulate policies that incentivize entrepreneurial ventures among students, including grants, startup seed funds, innovation awards, and structured mentorship opportunities. Such support would encourage practical application of creative cognition and positive personality traits in entrepreneurial pursuits.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the predictive influence of creative cognition and personality traits in entrepreneurial skills development among final-year undergraduate students at the University of Port Harcourt. The findings confirmed that creative cognition, along with key personality traits, namely extraversion, openness to experience, and conscientiousness significantly influence entrepreneurial skills development. Conversely, agreeableness and neuroticism did not predict entrepreneurial skills development. The results emphasize that both cognitive flexibility and personality dispositions are essential drivers of entrepreneurial success. Furthermore, the synergistic interaction between creativity and personality traits underscores the importance of a holistic approach to entrepreneurship education. By nurturing both creativity and positive personality traits, higher education institutions can better equip students for the challenges and opportunities of entrepreneurial careers in Nigeria and beyond.

REFERENCES

- Aboluwodi, A. (2018). Deploying Creative Thinking to Strengthen Entrepreneurial Capability Among University Students in Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Research*, 8(2), 93–108. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6341-9325>. Retrieved from <https://www.nepjol.info/index.php/JER/article/view/27381>
- Adebayo, O. S., & Kolawole, J. A. (2013). The historical background of entrepreneurial development in Nigeria: Its gains, shortcomings and needful. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences*, 4(5), 493-500
- Adeniji, S. (2024). Nigeria in Crisis Due to Youth Unemployment <https://www.africanliberty.org/2024/12/11/nigeria-in-crisis-due-to-youth-unemployment/>.
- Adenuga R, & Ayodele K. (2013). Adolescents' entrepreneurial behaviour: the predictive effect of the Big Five factors. *European Journal of Business and Social Sciences* 1(12): 48-58.
- Alhadihaq, M., Zakiah, S, Sudjatmoko, A., Winarno, A. & Hermana, D. (2024). How creative self efficacy foster entrepreneurial intention through creative process engagement in entrepreneurial higher education ecosystem. *Cogent Economics & Finance*. 12. 10.1080/23322039.2024.2370910.
- Amaechi-Udogu, V. C. (2020). Peer victimization and personality traits as predictors of social phobia among senior secondary school adolescents in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 8(4), 2980-2988.
- Cao, Y., Asad, M. M., Wang, L., Naz, A. & Almusharraf, N. (2022). Role of personality traits for entrepreneurial intentions of young entrepreneurs: A case study of higher education institution. *Frontier Psychology*; Volume 13 - 2022 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.1010412>
- Chen, Hong-xia. (2024). Exploring the Influence of Proactive Personality on Entrepreneurial Intention: The Mediating Role of Entrepreneurial Attitude and Moderating Effect of Perceived Educational Support Among University Students. *SAGE Open*. 14(1). Doi: [10.1177/21582440241233379](https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440241233379).

- Chukwudi, J & Nwosu, J. (2018). Entrepreneurship Education and the Challenges of Graduate Employability in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovation Management*. 9. 189-193. Doi: [10.18178/ijimt.2018.9.5.812](https://doi.org/10.18178/ijimt.2018.9.5.812)
- Costa, P. T., & McCrae, R. R. (1992). NEO personality inventory-revised (NEO-PI-R). Psychological Assessment Resources.
- Costa, P. T., & McCrae, R. R. (1996). The Five-Factor Model of Personality and its Relevance to Personality Disorders. *Journal of Personality Disorders*, 6(4), 261-273. <https://doi.org/10.1521/pedi.1992.6.4.343>
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2013). National Policy on Education (6th ed.). Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council. Abuja: NERDC Press
- Frese, M., & Gielnik, M. M. (2016). The psychology of entrepreneurship. In G. J. Boyle, J. G. O'Gorman, & G. J. Fogarty (Eds.), *Work and organisational psychology: Research methodology; Assessment and selection; Organisational change and development; Human resource and performance management; Emerging trends: Innovation/globalisation/technology* (pp. 89–122). Sage Publications, Inc.
- Hamidi, D. Y., Wennberg, K., & Berglund, H. (2008). Creativity in entrepreneurship education. *Journal of small business and enterprise development*, 15(2), 304-320. DOI: [10.1108/14626000810871691](https://doi.org/10.1108/14626000810871691)
- Hood, J. N. and Young, J. E. (1993). Entrepreneurship's requisite areas of development: A survey of top executives in successful entrepreneurial firms. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 8, 115-135.
- Khalaf, S. (2024), "Conscientiousness and entrepreneurship", *Review of Behavioral Finance*, Vol. 16 No. 4, pp. 754-771. <https://doi.org/10.1108/RBF-05-2023-0150>.
- Kollmann, T., Stöckmann, C., Linstaedt, J, W. & Kensbock, J. M. (2021). Personality composition and performance in entrepreneurial teams: understanding the impact of stability and plasticity traits in a relative contribution model. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Venturing* Vol. 13(3), 262-287 <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJEV.2021.116840>
- Lebuda, I., & Benedek, M. (2023). A systematic framework of creative metacognition. *Physics of Life Reviews*, 46(1) DOI: [10.1016/j.plrev.2023.07.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plrev.2023.07.002)
- Leutner, F., Ahmetoglu, G., Akhtar, R. & Chamorro-Premuzic, T. (2014). "The Relationship between the Entrepreneurial Personality and the Big Five Personality Traits." *Personality and Individual Differences* 63:58–63. *Personality and Individual Differences* 63:58-63. DOI: [10.1016/j.paid.2014.01.042](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2014.01.042).
- Li L-N, Huang J-H and Gao, S-Y(2022) The Relationship Between Personality Traits and Entrepreneurial Intention Among College Students: The Mediating Role of Creativity. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13:82220. DOI: [10.3389/fpsyg.2022.822206](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.822206)
- Liu, H., Kulturel-Konak, S., & Konak, A. (2021). Key elements and their roles in entrepreneurship education ecosystem: Comparative review and suggestions for sustainability. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(19), 10648. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su131910648>.
- Mbon, U. F, Offem, O. O. & Odey, D. A. (2023). Repositioning entrepreneurial education planning and skill acquisition for economic recovery and sustainability in the post-COVID-19 era. *Global Journal of Educational Research*, 22(2), 225-235. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.4314/gjedr.v22i2.13>.
- Mensah, I.K., Khan, M.K. & Mwakapesa, D.S. (2023). Factors determining the entrepreneurial intentions among Chinese university students: the moderating impact of student internship motivation. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10, 1-15; 752. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-02275-9>.
- Mumford, M. D., Martin, R., Elliott, S., & McIntosh, T. (2020). Creative Failure: Why Can't People Solve Creative Problems. *Journal of Creative Behavior*, 54(2), 378-394. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jocb.372>.

- National Bureau of Statistics, (2023). *Nigeria unemployment rate report 2023*. National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria.
- National Youth Development Policy (UNDP). (2019). *Enhancing Youth Development and Participation in the context of Sustainable Development*, Federal Ministry of Youth and Sports Development 2019 Edition Federal Government of Nigeria.
- Obialo, Felix-Kingsley (2020) Fostering creativity and innovation for business success: A Nigerian perspective. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 7(10), 1–10. <https://oapub.org/edu/index.php/ejes/article/view/3323>
- Obschonka, M., and Stuetzer, M. (2017). Integrating psychological approaches to entrepreneurship: the Entrepreneurial Personality System (EPS). *Small Bus. Econ.* 49, 203–231. doi: 10.1007/s11187-016-9821-y.
- OECD. (2019). *OECD SME and Entrepreneurship Outlook 2019*. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. <https://doi.org/10.1787/34907e9c-en>
- Ofor Douglas, S. (2024). Entrepreneurship education for self- reliance in a depressed economy: The case of university education system in Nigeria. *Journal of international, educational research and development*, 11(2), 66-76.
- Ogwugwua, Q. O., & Mbah, S. I. (2024). Entrepreneurial personality traits and sustainability of entrepreneurship in Delta State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management Research*, 5(3), 303-325.
- Okolie, U. C., Igwe, P. A., Ayoola, A. A., Nwosu, H. E., Kanu, C. & Mong, I. K. (2021). Entrepreneurial competencies of undergraduate students: the case of universities in Nigeria. *International Journal of Management Education*, 19, [10.1016/j.ijme.2021.100452](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2021.100452)
- Oyinlola, M, Kolade, O, Okoya, S. A, Ajala, O, Adefila, A., Adediji, A, Babaremu, K, Tijani, B, Adejuwon, J, Wambui, F. & Akinlabi, E. T. (2024). Entrepreneurship and innovation in Nigerian universities: Trends, challenges and opportunities. *Heliyon*, 10(9), e29940, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e29940>.
- Rauch, A. and Frese, M. (2007) Let's Put the Person Back into Entrepreneurship Research: A Meta-Analysis on the Relationship between Business Owners' Personality Traits, Business Creation, and Success. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 16(4), 353-385. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13594320701595438>
- Runco, M. & Acar, S. (2012). Divergent Thinking as an Indicator of Creative Potential. *Creativity Research Journal* 24(1):66-75. DOI: [10.1080/10400419.2012.652929](https://doi.org/10.1080/10400419.2012.652929)
- Runco, M. A. (2023). Updating the standard definition of creativity to account for the artificial creativity of AI. *Creativity Research Journal*, 37(1), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10400419.2023.2257977>.
- Sun, S., Zhao, Y., & Tan, Y. (2022). *The Influence of Openness to Experience on Entrepreneurial Success: An Empirical Study of Chinese Entrepreneurs*. *Journal of Business Research*, 137, 119-128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.08.061>
- Tantawy, M., Herbert, K., McNally, J. J., Mengel, T., Piperopoulos, P., & Foord, D. (2021). Bringing creativity back to entrepreneurship education: Creative self-efficacy, creative process engagement, and entrepreneurial intentions. *Journal of Business Venturing Insights*, 15, e00239. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbvi.2021.e00239>.
- Uche, L., & Adegboyega, O. (2022). *Conscientiousness and Entrepreneurial Aspirations: Evidence from Nigerian University Students*. *African Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, 13(2), 221-237. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJEMS-05-2021-0248>
- Usoro, I. A, & Brownson, C. D. (2024). Creative Thinking, Adaptability and Entrepreneurial Development in Nigeria. *British Journal of Management and Marketing Studies*. 7(1). 69-77. <https://doi.org/10.52589/BJMMS-96UF1ZBT>.
- Uzonwanne-Obianefo R.N., Igweh K.F. and Obianefo C.A. (2021). Entrepreneurial insight of youths toward job creation arising from COVID-19 in delta state, Nigeria. *International Journal of*

Research in Human Resource Management, 3(2): 124-133

DOI: [10.33545/26633213.2021.v3.i2b.80](https://doi.org/10.33545/26633213.2021.v3.i2b.80)

- Ward, T. B., Saunders, K. N., & Dodds, R. A. (1999). Creative cognition in gifted adolescents. *Roeper Review*, 21(4), 260-266.
- Wu, Keqiang & Zhao, Xin & Wang, Xinyu & Chen, Xiongying & Hung, Tsang Kai & Wang, Zijun & Lee, Shu-Chuan. (2023). The Impact of Entrepreneurial Resilience on the Entrepreneurial Intention of Return Migrants: An Empirical Study Based on Survey Data From Multiple Provinces in China. *SAGE Open*. 13. 10.1177/21582440231182654.
- Yu X, Zhao X and Hou Y (2023) Cognitive flexibility and entrepreneurial creativity: the chain mediating effect of entrepreneurial alertness and entrepreneurial self-efficacy. *Frontier Psychology*; 14:1292797. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1292797.
- Zampetakis, L. A., & Moustakis, V. (2006). Linking creativity with entrepreneurial intentions: A structural approach. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*, 2(3), 413–428. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11365-006-0006-z>
- Zhao, H., & Seibert, S. E. (2006). The Big Five personality dimensions and entrepreneurial status: A meta-analytical review. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 91(2), 259–271. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.91.2.259>
- Zhao, Hao & Seibert, Scott & Lumpkin, G. (2010). The Relationship of Personality to Entrepreneurial Intentions and Performance: A Meta-Analytic Review. *Journal of Management - J MANAGE*. 36. 381-404. 10.1177/0149206309335187.